

1 New compact ion source design and implementation for low 2 current applications

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6 **Abstract**

A new compact electron cyclotron resonance (ECR) ion source for low current applications, designed and built in-house at the University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU) is presented. The source was designed to use as many commercially available components as possible for key tasks such as electromagnetic resonators, magnetic structure, RF power couplers and beam transport, to lower the cost and lessen reliance on specially made parts for spares. This leads to a cost-effective yet compact and fully functional design. The main design decisions are described and experiments on plasma generation and the proton beam extracted using the source are shown and discussed.

7 *Keywords:* , Ion Sources, Electron cyclotron resonance, Low current

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9 **1. Introduction**

10 Ion sources have always been important for high energy physics [1] but increasingly
11 have gained relevance for industry, ion implantation and bio-medical environments
12 [2]. However, most are still expensive and bulky. Their technology is a very active
13 field of research, with clear scientific and economic interest [3].

14 Electron cyclotron resonance ion sources (ECRIS) have become one of the most
15 common means for ion production in basic research and industry for a wide range of
16 applications because of their reliability and capability to produce multiply charged
17 ion beams from most stable elements [4]. Although much research effort has been

18 devoted in the past to the design and development of high current, high energy
19 sources, mostly in the context of large scientific facilities, lower current devices are
20 of paramount importance in medical [5] [6] and industrial applications [7], as well
21 as in low energy surface and atomic physics experiments [8], among other fields.
22 Although many contemporary ion source designs are based on experience gathered
23 from their preceding high energy physics examples, low current, low energy ion
24 sources can be designed essentially from scratch so there is no need for them to be
25 bulky or need specialty setups.

26 We present our new design for a compact and cost effective electron cyclotron
27 resonance (ECR) multi-species ion source for low current applications, designed
28 and built by the authors at the University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU).
29 The key factors chosen to achieve compactness and cost effectiveness are: a plasma
30 chamber built using standard vacuum components, a permanent magnet Halbach
31 structure to generate the ECR field, a simple RF coupler in chamber, RF power
32 transmission over coaxial cables everywhere except for the DC break, and solid
33 state power amplifiers.

34 It is difficult to compare ion sources, even among ECR ion sources, because the
35 design parameters, the species and for what they will be used are so varied. This
36 task is simpler if only high current proton or H^- sources for large projects are
37 compared, where the beam currents are between 30 and 100 mA, and their emit-
38 tances between 0.2 and $0.3 \pi \text{ mm mrad}$ [9]. However as soon as the application is
39 different, the spread in the parameters becomes larger with currents ranging from
40 a few μA to tens of mA and emittances from 0.01 to almost $100 \pi \text{ mm mrad}$
41 [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20].

42 **2. Description of the source**

43 The ion source is conceived for low current industrial and bio applications. Based
44 on ECR principles, the main design parameters are summarized in Table 1. Al-
45 though the table refers to H_2 , the ion source can be operated with gases other
46 than Hydrogen, for instance for Helium, Nitrogen or any other elemental gas for
47 ion production. No major changes would be needed other than the use of the
48 appropriate pressure regulator. This will be tested in the near future.

Table 1: Main design parameters of PIT30 ion source

ECRIS Parameters	
Microwave frequency	3 GHz
Microwave power	<100 W
Gas mass flow	<5 sccm (H_2)
Magnetic field	110 mT
Extraction voltage	<20 kV
Beam current	<50 μ A (H^+)
Beam emittance	<0.2 π mm mrad

49 A large variety of technologies had to be integrated in the source, and made to work
 50 in harmony: Mechanical, electromagnetic, vacuum, RF, high voltage and control.
 51 And while the design of all these elements has to be carried out simultaneously,
 52 because they are not independent of each other, for the structure of this paper,
 53 the criteria used in the design of each subsystem and the relation between these
 54 is detailed below in independent sections. 3GHz was chosen because solid state
 55 amplifiers for that frequency are commercially available, and the extracted current
 56 will be higher than for 2.45 GHz given that the current scales with the square to
 57 the frequency [21].

58 *2.1. Mechanical design*

59 The main design decision taken in the design of the ion source was to use standard
 60 vacuum components in as much as possible, including the plasma chamber and the
 61 High Voltage isolators. More specifically conflat (CF) components were chosen,
 62 since the use of copper gaskets that are plastically deformed to achieve the vacuum
 63 seal has the additional advantage that it guarantees good electrical contact between
 64 the different components. In places where an even better electrical contact is
 65 required, silver plated gaskets were used, like at the plasma chamber. This type of
 66 seal is also more resistant to higher temperatures, as may be the case in the plasma
 67 chamber. The cost of the ion source was reduced by using these components, since
 68 there are several companies that manufacture them with very tight mechanical
 69 tolerances. Only a few one-of-a-kind parts were used, since specially made parts
 70 are more expensive than standard ones. Figure 1 shows a CAD rendered schematic

71 in cross-section of what the plasma chamber built from standard components looks
 72 like. The model was made using DN 63 CF and and DN 100 CF components
 73 purchased from Vacom, Germany [22].

Figure 1: Cross section of a CAD drawing of the proposed plasma chamber made from standard CF components. 1) gas inlet, 2) RF port, 3) magnetic structure, 4) plasma chamber, 5) extraction electrodes, 6) Turbomolecular pump port, 7) pressure sensor 8) Faraday cup/ Scintillator screen port. The entire assembly shown is 600 mm long.

74 2.2. Electromagnetic design

75 2.2.1. Plasma chamber

76 Since the plasma chamber was designed as a circular waveguide, for our choice of
 77 frequency the smallest commercial diameter that would act as a resonant cavity for
 78 the CF flange system was DN 63. The axial length of the chamber was calculated
 79 using analytical formulae, but because the power would have to be coupled using a
 80 loop or an antenna that would break the circular symmetry of the system, full 3D
 81 finite element simulations were used to verify the analytical calculations. Figure 2
 82 shows a simulation of the chamber with the antenna coupler. The antenna coupler
 83 was chosen because it is simpler to make than a loop, it simply press-fits to the
 84 center pin of the rf feedthrough, it is compact and directly excites the TE_{111} mode
 85 at which the cavity resonates.

Figure 2: Preliminary simulation of the electric field in the plasma chamber generated by a 3 GHz drive.

86 As mentioned before, in order to reduce the cost and simplify the operation of
 87 the source, there is no electrical power supply on the high voltage end of the
 88 source. In order to generate the magnetic field needed in the chamber for the
 89 free electrons to resonate, permanent magnets were used. The intensity of the
 90 field needed was calculated from the equation for the resonant frequency of a free
 91 electron in a magnetic field ($B = 2\pi f \frac{m}{e}$, where B is the magnetic inductance,
 92 f is the frequency of the microwaves used, m and e are respectively the mass
 93 and charge of the electron). For the 3 GHz microwaves planned, this results in
 94 a field of approximately 110 mT. A Halbach type configuration made up of eight
 95 permanent magnet bars was designed to generate an axial magnetic field parallel
 96 to the plasma chamber. The diameter of the plasma chamber was chosen to be
 97 as small as possible in order to minimize the volume of the permanent magnets
 98 needed to generate the ECR field. Figure 3 shows that a field of about 110 mT
 99 in the center of the chamber is achieved. Magnetically soft iron (Armco[®] Pure

100 Iron) pieces at both ends are used to close the magnetic flux and confine it to the
101 plasma chamber. The soft Iron piece at the beam extraction end of the chamber
102 also doubles as the first electrode in the extraction system and helps to reduce the
103 magnetic field in the extraction region of the source.

Figure 3: Simulation of the magnetic field in the plasma chamber generated by an arrangement of 8 permanent magnet bars evenly spaced around the circumference of the chamber and two soft iron pieces to help close the magnetic flux. One of the pieces also doubles as the first electrode for the extraction system

104 In Figure 4 it is also shown a photograph of the plasma chamber together with the
105 Halbach permanent magnet array, which has proved to be efficient for Hydrogen
106 plasma production [23].

Figure 4: *Photograph of the Halbach array mounted on the plasma chamber.*

107 *2.2.2. Beam extraction and optics*

108 Beam extraction is achieved through the use of a tetrode system. The first elec-
 109 trode as mentioned before also doubles as part of the magnetic system of the
 110 plasma chamber, and it has a 5 mm diameter extraction aperture with a chamfer
 111 at the pierce angle. This first electrode along with the plasma chamber are at the
 112 extraction voltage (30 kV maximum). This is followed by a set of three electrodes
 113 that are configured to work as an Einzel lens [24]. The second and fourth elec-
 114 trodes are connected to ground and the third electrode (central electrode in the
 115 Einzel lens) is connected to a high voltage supply, which can be varied to achieve
 116 the desired beam focus. The effect of varying this voltage is demonstrated in the
 117 results section. The inset of figure 11 shows a simulation of the extraction system
 118 using SimIon[®], and shows the numbering of the electrodes.

119 *2.2.3. DC break*

120 In order to supply the plasma chamber with RF power a DC break is used. It is
121 made from two coaxial N to WG 284 waveguide transitions facing each other and
122 separated by a narrow nylon separator with a central gap. The nylon piece serves
123 both as an electrical insulator for DC voltages and as the mechanical clamp that
124 holds the two waveguides together. A cross section of the DC break's construction
125 can be seen in Figure 5. The design was tested in DC by connecting one waveguide
126 to ground and the other one to 30 kV. No current was registered on the power
127 supply during the test. The setup was then also tested at the chosen frequency of 3
128 GHz to verify the correct transmission of RF power. Fig 6 shows the measured RF
129 scattering parameters S_{11} and S_{21} for the DC break as a function of frequency,
130 where as it can be seen the RF losses at 3 GHz are only -14.8 dB. The losses during
131 operation result in less than a 5° C increase in the temperature of the DC break
132 when the steady state is reached.

Figure 5: *Cross-section of the DC break, 1 and 3 are standard N to WG 284 transitions, 2 is the custom made nylon separator.*

Figure 6: Measured RF scattering parameters in dB (S_{11}) (adaptation) and (S_{21}) (loss) as a function of frequency for the DC break centered around 3 GHz.

133 2.3. Vacuum system

134 The vacuum pumps for the system were dimensioned by simulating the vacuum
 135 system using *Molflow+* [25]. The system is composed of a turbomolecular pump
 136 (Pfeiffer HiPace 400) and a dry roughing pump (Adixen/Pfeiffer ACP 15) to gen-
 137 erate the vacuum, together with a gas mass flow controller (Omega FMA-2615A)
 138 to supply the gas to be ionized. The mass flow controller provides quantity of
 139 gas independently of variations in ambient temperature. The base pressure of the
 140 system reaches 5×10^{-8} mbar and during operation is in the 10^{-4} mbar range with
 141 gas flowing between 2 and 4 sccm of Hydrogen.

142 2.4. Radio frequency power supply chain

143 This comprises all the elements required to generate, adapt and measure the RF
144 power used to generate the ECR plasma. A schematic of the components that
145 make up the RF power supply chain can be seen in Figure 7. A low power signal
146 (0 dBm max) is generated using a function generator (Agilent E 4432b) and then
147 amplified using a GaN solid state amplifier developed for instrumentation and
148 radiocommunication applications (MCS model AMP-2G-6G-50dBm-R) that can
149 output up to 100 W in continuous wave mode. The output of the generator is
150 connected to a circulator (Konnect RF, P/N: KCI 177237) and a load to protect
151 the amplifier in case too much power is reflected. The RF power then goes through
152 a dual directional coupler into a tree stub tuner (Maury microwave model 1878B),
153 and then through a second dual directional coupler. The power then goes into
154 the DC break described before and finally into the plasma chamber. The three
155 stub tuner is used to match the impedance of the plasma chamber to the rest
156 of the RF system and maximize power transmission to the plasma. The first
157 directional coupler is used to measure the output of the amplifier while the second
158 one measures the power reflected by the chamber. All the connections between the
159 elements mentioned before are done using coaxial cables with N-type connectors.

Figure 7: Schematic of the elements that make up the RF Chain used to generate the plasma in the ion source. The monitoring system takes care of all the measurements from the directional couplers.

160 *2.5. High voltage system*

161 The extraction and acceleration of the charged particles generated in the plasma
162 is achieved by raising the plasma chamber to a high voltage (up to 30 kV) rela-
163 tive to ground using an adjustable power supply (Technix SR30-P-150-OP). The
164 plasma chamber is mechanically supported using commercial isolators rated to 30
165 kV normally used for medium voltage power lines. The chamber is electrically
166 separated from the rest of the vacuum system using an alumina insulator tube
167 brazed to CF flanges available commercially and rated to 60 kV. Gas is supplied
168 to the chamber through a 3 mm polyamide tube that is electrically insulating.
169 Beam focusing is achieved by supplying the 3rd electrode in the tetrode electrode
170 described before with a second programmable power supply (Stanford Research Sys-
171 tems PS350/5000V-25W) that can output up to ± 5 kV. Both power supplies were
172 chosen so that they can maintain a current higher than the maximum beam cur-
173 rent in their whole operating ranges. 30 kV was chosen because it is the highest
174 voltage that fits the Spanish legal definition of a mid tension installation.

175 For safety reasons all metallic components in the system (with the exception of the
176 plasma chamber and magnet system) are connected to ground. Care was taken
177 to avoid in as much as possible ground loops and to ensure that all connections
178 had the highest possible conductivity [26]. The plasma chamber is enclosed in a
179 Faraday cage made from aluminum perforated plates connected to ground so that
180 the chamber is well ventilated because it relies on natural convection for this end.
181 Apart from EM insulation of the source, the main purpose of the Faraday cage is
182 to act as a physical barrier between the chamber and any living creature during
183 operation of the source.

184 *2.6. Control and monitoring*

185 In provision of future additions to the source, a National Instruments PXI (PXIe-
186 1082) chassis with a real time controller (PXIe-8108) with a front end programmed
187 in LabVIEW is used to monitor and control all the signals in the system. For future
188 applications this configuration has the advantage that it can handle all the timing
189 signals needed to synchronize RF-based accelerating elements and diagnostics. The
190 power supplies, the amperemeter and the RF function generator are controlled via

191 their IEEE 488 interfaces from the LabVIEW program. All analog signals are
192 handled in the PXI using a PXIe-6259 DAQ card in the PXI chassis.

193 **3. Beam measurements**

194 Once the ion source was fully assembled and the individual components were tested
195 separately, beam extraction experiments were carried out in order to validate the
196 operability of the complete ion source. Figure 8 shows a photograph of the ion
197 source as it stands, and where most of the elements described in the previous sec-
198 tions can be seen. At this point due to regulatory limitations 10 keV could not be
199 surpassed. Three types of experiments were carried out in order to characterize
200 the extracted beam. First, in order to verify the beam alignment, a P43 phospho-
201 rescent screen was used to look at both the position and the size of the beam spot.
202 The misalignment of the beam was corrected by adjusting a vacuum port aligner
203 placed between the alumina isolator and the pumping vessel. The total distance
204 between the last electrode and the plane where all the measurements were carried
205 out was approximately 600 mm. In Figure 9 we see the beam spot, where the
206 brighter and darker spots on the left and top of the spot are due to prior damage
207 to the P43 coating. In any case, the spot can be estimated to be less than 20 mm
208 in diameter.

Figure 8: Photograph of the ion source as tested with one of the protective panels removed. 1) DC break, 2) Gas inlet tube, 3) Permanent magnet structure around plasma chamber, 4) High voltage stand-offs 5) Alumina isolator, 6) Port aligner, 7) Turbomolecular pump, 8) Pressure sensor, 9) Mass flow controller, 10) P43 scintillator screen.

Figure 9: Image of the 6 keV beam spot on the phosphorescent screen when focused to the smallest size achievable (3.8 kV in electrode 3). The areas enclosed by the red dotted lines are the previously damaged areas.

209 If the intensity as a function of position of the image is analyzed, we can see that
210 the intensity follows a gaussian distribution. This is shown in Figure 10, where
211 the measured data (semi-transparent) are laid over the 2D gaussian that best fits
212 the data. Despite the unevenness in the image due to the damaged screen a very
213 reasonable fit is achieved ($R^2=0.93$). The portions of the image that correspond
214 to the damaged sections of the screen have been marked by a red dashed line that
215 surrounds the perimeter of the damaged area.

Figure 10: Image intensity for a 6 keV beam spot on the phosphorescent screen when focused to the smallest size achievable (3.8 kV in the central electrode of the Einzel lens).

216 Second, with the beam centered on the furthestmost port down beam, the phospho-
 217 rescent screen was replaced with a Faraday cup (Kimball Physics FC-73) connected
 218 to an amperemeter (Keithley Model 6430). A fixed extraction voltage was set and
 219 the Einzel lens voltage (electrode 3) was varied, as is seen in Figure 11. At first
 220 with increasing voltage an increased current was measured in the Faraday cup
 221 until a maximum was reached. Then, if the voltage was further increased, the
 222 measured current decreased. This is consistent with what was seen on the phos-
 223 phorescent screen: the highest current and the smallest spot were observed at the
 224 same Einzel lens voltage for the same extraction potential. It should be noted that
 225 if both voltages were maintained, but the plasma was extinguished by turning off
 226 the RF power, no current was measured on the Faraday cup, and no image was
 227 longer visible on the screen, as expected.

228 With the data from Figure 11, the spot size (obtained from Figure 9), the diameter
 229 of the Faraday cup (\varnothing 5 mm) and the fit to a Gaussian peak from Figure 10 we
 230 can calculate the total current in the beam spot. We get that the current in the

231 spot is approximately 6.25 times greater than what the Faraday cup captures,
 232 resulting in a total current of $4.3 \mu\text{A}$ at 6 keV.

Figure 11: Beam current measured at the Faraday cup for a 6 keV beam as a function of the voltage applied to the central electrode of the Einzel lens.

233 Third, in order to evaluate the emittance of the source at the previous conditions, a
 234 pepperpot was installed. It consisted of a plate with a rectangular array of 0.45 mm
 235 holes spaced 1.27 mm between centers placed 37 mm from the scintillating screen.
 236 Following the procedure outlined by Zhang [28] the beam emittance was calculated,
 237 and the highest value was obtained for the horizontal direction ($0.065 \pi \text{ mm mrad}$).
 238 Figure 12 shows the plots of divergence vs. position measured for the beam. The
 239 result is a narrow ellipse whose tilt indicates that, as should be expected, the beam
 240 is divergent. The emittance values obtained are very reasonable and comparable
 241 to other sources.

Figure 12: Horizontal and vertical divergence vs. position for a 6 keV beam, with 3.8 kV in the central electrode of the Einzel lens, obtained from the pepperpot images.

242 4. Conclusions

243 A newly designed compact electron cyclotron resonance (ECR) multi-species ion
 244 source for low current applications has been built and tested. As a key ingredi-
 245 ent of the design, we have shown that using mostly off-the-shelf components is a
 246 viable way to construct a low cost yet perfectly functional off resonance ECR ion
 247 source. By keeping the RF power low (≤ 100 W) air cooling has been proved to be
 248 sufficient to keep the temperature of the permanent magnet assembly below the
 249 demagnetization temperature of 80°C for the N50 FeNdB magnets used, leading
 250 to a simplified source design that doesn't require any ancillary supplies on the
 251 high voltage end. The beam generated has a low emittance and a small spot size,

252 suitable for a number of applications where low currents are needed, including
253 biomedical and industrial uses. Because of its compactness, simplified magnetic
254 structure, low power requirements, efficiency, quality of beam and straightforward
255 operation, the presented source compares favorably, for smaller-scale applications,
256 to other traditional ion source designs, typically conceived for large-scale particle
257 accelerators or large scientific facilities, which may not be as convenient nor as
258 cost-effective for industrial or medical applications in smaller environments.

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